

ARTHROSCOPIC DIAGNOSIS OF INJURIES AND DISEASES OF THE KNEE JOINT IN CHILDREN

Keywords— knee joint, children, arthroscopy, injuries, meniscus, anterior cruciate ligament

I. INTRODUCTION

Knee joint injuries are among the most common musculoskeletal injuries in children. The knee joint is the largest joint in the human body and represents a complex biomechanical system with numerous anatomical structures prone to injury.

Closed knee joint injuries in children account for 5% to 20% of all patients requiring emergency hospitalization in trauma departments [1], [3], [4]. Diagnosis is complicated by difficulties in determining the mechanism of injury in children, their negative response to clinical examination, and the presence of many radiolucent structures within the joint cavity.

The use of modern non-invasive diagnostic methods such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and ultrasound (US) has significantly improved the detection of intra-articular injuries. According to Merkulov V.N. et al., the accuracy of preoperative diagnosis in children has reached 86.8% [2].

Recently, arthroscopy has been increasingly used as a minimally invasive surgical method for early detection and treatment of knee joint injuries in children, especially those associated with secondary cartilage changes.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

We analyzed the results of arthroscopic examination of the knee joint in 74 patients (40 girls and 34 boys) treated at the pediatric orthopedic and trauma department of the Grodno Emergency Hospital. The age of patients ranged from 10 to 17 years.

Diagnostic methods included: medical history analysis, physical examination, functional tests, X-ray examination in two standard projections, computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI).

Indications for arthroscopy included: hemarthrosis with intra-articular osteochondral fragments, chronic knee injuries with persistent symptoms, patellar instability syndrome with dislocations, knee joint locking with suspected meniscus injury, clinical signs of cruciate ligament injury.

Arthroscopy was performed under general anesthesia in a fluid medium using standard portals. In most cases, diagnostic arthroscopy was followed by therapeutic intervention.

The therapeutic value of arthroscopy includes not only surgical treatment but also lavage of the joint cavity with 0.9% NaCl, removing blood clots, fibrin, tissue debris, microorganisms, and immune complexes.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Half of the patients with traumatic knee injuries were professional athletes, with a predominance of girls.

Right and left knee joints were affected with similar frequency ($p > 0.05$). The most common injuries were: anterior cruciate ligament (23 cases), medial meniscus (19 cases), lateral meniscus (8 cases).

Among femoral condyle injuries, subchondral damage of the lateral condyle was most common (10 cases), compared to only 3 cases involving the medial condyle.

Free intra-articular fragments, if left untreated, may cause chronic hypertrophic synovitis and joint blockage. Osteochondral fragments were removed in all patients. In some cases, discrepancies were observed between radiographic and arthroscopic localization due to fragment migration during the procedure.

Non-traumatic conditions were also identified. Three patients were diagnosed with chronic diseases: Koenig's disease, Hoffa's disease, Kashin-Beck disease (one case each).

Preliminary diagnoses based on clinical and radiological findings did not match arthroscopic findings in 70% of cases. In some patients, imaging suggested intra-articular damage, but arthroscopy did not confirm these findings.

Treatment outcomes showed restoration of knee joint function in more than 90% of cases.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The most common indications for arthroscopic diagnosis in children are acute and chronic injuries of the anterior cruciate ligament and medial meniscus. Patellar injuries are less frequent and usually occur during dislocation.

Comprehensive diagnostics using modern imaging techniques combined with arthroscopy allows effective diagnosis and treatment of intra-articular soft tissue injuries, resulting in functional recovery in 90% of cases.

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